

Additional File 3: Uncropped blots Figure 3A

Limits of the displayed area in Figure 3A

M Protein marker lane

Additional File 3: Uncropped blots Figure 4B

 Limits of the displayed area in Figure 4B

M **Protein marker lane**

Additional File 3: Uncropped blots Figure 6A

Limits of the displayed area in Figure 6A

M

Protein marker lane